

Data Management Plan in Slovenia

Action plan for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources

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International initiatives for 'open data'

Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding (OECD, 2007)

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European Commission Research & Innovation. Policy Initiatives

Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport
funded a project

'OPEN DATA'

**Action plan for establishing a system of open access to research data funded
by public sources**

,Open data` in Slovenia

The main goal of the **Open Data project** was to prepare a **policy and a strategy**, needed for establishing a system of open access to research data in Slovenia

When, in which cases and how to open research data?

Principle of Flexibility: *„Specific national, social, economic and regulatory implications should be considered when organisations develop research data access arrangements, and when governments develop policies to promote data access and review the implementation of these Principles and Guidelines.’* (OECD, 2007, 15)

Methodology/Approach: ,bottom to top`

The principle of flexibility can be achieved through understanding the current situation:

1) 22 semi-structured interviews:

- researchers, librarians, heads of research institutes
- 10 research institutes, 6 faculties
- 17 research disciplines: physics, biology, medicine, civil engineering, archeology, social work, economy, musicology, anthropology, languages...

2) 3 workshops:

- Workshop 1: Problems and Solutions in the Field of Data Services in Slovenia
- Workshop 2: Policy of Research Data Management in Slovenia
- Workshop 3: Advanced Technology for Establishing Data Infrastructure in Slovenia

3) Individual working visits/consultations:

- Information Commissioner
- Intellectual Property Institute
- Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts
- DARIAH, CLARIN representatives in Slovenia ...

What we found out?

Regarding documentation, retention and access to research data in Slovenia:

- Researchers have different habits and views
- Research institutes follow disunited, unwritten rules and practices

But mainly they face identical problems:

lack of knowledge, time and finances for dealing with research data,
extremely competitive scientific environment

What we found out?

Major barriers in achieving open data:

- 1) big **differences in the development** of data infrastructure and services
- 2) **dilemmas and fears** emerging from questions **related to law** (intellectual property, personal data protection)
- 3) absence of **culture of data sharing**
- 4) **absence of framework policy**, which would help in research data management

Researchers mainly understand that **open access is a must**, they are aware of disorder.

And express the need of developing a framework policy and rules by which the system would be justly organized and would provide service to researchers (data creators and data users).

Proposed solution:

To overcome the differences in development of infrastructure and services, expectations of researchers, capabilities of funders and diversity of disciplines (formats, methods etc.)

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

is proposed as obligatory part of research project documentation

To achieve long-term access to research data DMP should refer to following goals:

- to plan who, when and how will deal with data
- to support greater efficiency and quality in data creation and data documentation
- to assure ethic and legal compliance: ethical issues, copy right and intellectual property rights
- to take data preservation action during carrying out research
- to make plans for depositing data (where, taking requests of data centre into account)
- to assure that data management accords with disciplinary norms, with framework policies and institutional policies
- to define importance of data for long-term preservation: selection and preservation plan

Data Management Plan

„Open data“ project ended in September 2013, its main deliverables were:

- a proposal for an **action plan** for establishing a system of open access to research data funded by public sources in Slovenia and
- a draft of **national policy** of dealing with research data

Both of them include Data Management Plan as a basic tool/formal ground, which interrelates different actors (researchers, funders, data centres, libraries) and defines their roles and responsibilities.

Data management plan is proposed as:

- an obligatory part of research documentation of the project proposals financed by public funds
- it ensures that technical and legal relevance of data is achieved, before depositing data to a data centre

Draft of the National Policy consists of

1. Introduction:

- motives for policy and its purpose
- roles and responsibility
- policy consists of elements, leading to sustainable system and framework for data management

2. Provisions of policy:

- obligations of researchers
- responsibility of institutions
- obligations and rights of public funders

3. Conclusions

DMP in a framework Policy

In the draft of policy data management plan is mentioned 16 times as a tool for helping to organize research infrastructure and service .

What has to be done?

- research institutions have to prepare their institutional policies which later on serve as a framework for preparing DMP (roles, responsibilities, support etc.)
- establishment of support services, needed for preparing and implementation of DMP
- establishment of support infrastructure for implementation of DMP
- disciplinary data centres in cooperation with research libraries and IT organize and provide services of guidance, training and support in preparing and implementation of DMP

DMP includes:

- details of how the framework policy will be carried out
- long-term importance for science, uniqueness and usability of data, recommended place of deposit (disciplinary data centre) – it is a founding ground for future (long-term) data management plan
- has to include argued explanation of the need to create new data (why existing data does not fulfill needs of the project)
- can include a statement that a project does not foresee creation of research data

DMP in a framework Policy

Obligations and rights of public funders

Register of DMPs and register of research data, are interrelated to existing scientific informational systems, used for evaluation of scientific work (scientific credits).

DMP goes through peer review process and its assessment is part of the project evaluation.

DMP is a componentpart of project documentation, used by funding agency to control if a registered plan is fulfilled out as planned.

Proposal for an action plan consists of:

1. Responsibilities of the Ministry, representatives of scientific community and professional associations
2. Development of data infrastructure
3. Motivating researchers and research institutions for approaching open data access
4. Maintenance of services, which support dealing with data, data evaluation, selection, deposit, digital retention and access to data
5. Publishers and their role for responsible dealing with research data in scientific publications

DMP is mentioned 17 times

DMP in a proposal of Action Plan

How to motivate researchers to share data in a proper way?

1) Terms and conditions for DM

- DMP is accepted as mandatory part of project documentation by funders and scientific community
- existing register of scientific work (projects, publications) in Slovenia (SICRIS) has to be adopted in a way, that includes information about DMP
- a register/evidence of DMP has to be established, relating to the existing system of scientific work in Slovenia (SICRIS, COBISS)
- funding agency assures up to 10 % of the project money for additional work needed to prepare and deposit data in the open access environment, estimated costs are included in a DMP

2) Support, guidance and control in DM performance

- disciplinary data centres in cooperation with related services (libraries) offer support and guidance in preparing DMP
- a system has to be established to control implementation of DMP – a function performed by disciplinary data centre (authorized by funding agency)
- a research infrastructure has to be established to perform data services as a support in preparing DMP

Further steps

A draft of framework policy and a proposal of action plan are planned to go through public debate open to anybody who is dealing with research data funded by public funds.

Open discussion should focus on:

- **benefits**
- **costs**
- **Development of infrastructure and services ...**

The idea of DMP has to be adopted by researchers and research institutes, but inclusion of DMP in framework policy and action plan can speed up this process.